

**METHODS OF TEACHING CHEMISTRY IN SCHOOLS: MODERN
APPROACH AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES**

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Annotation: This article analyzes the methodology of teaching chemistry in schools, modern pedagogical approaches, and the possibilities of applying innovative technologies. It discusses the necessity of transitioning from traditional methods to modern approaches in teaching chemistry, which aims to enhance students' motivation and improve the quality of education. The article also highlights the advantages of implementing interactive methods and new pedagogical technologies in teaching.

Keywords: Chemistry teaching methodology, modern pedagogy, innovative technologies, school education, didactics, student participation, problem-based learning, experiential learning

introduction

Today, chemistry gives students not only an important place in the framework of natural sciences, but also plays an important role in the development of scientific thinking, the formation of analytical thinking skills and the development of practical skills. However, there are challenges faced in the learning process, such as keeping students motivated and adopting new teaching methodologies. This article will talk about modern approaches to teaching chemistry and advanced pedagogical technologies.

A teacher is required to be very attentive when teaching chemistry, because even one small mistake is bound to lead to confusion. In most cases, schoolchildren are not interested in chemistry, because chemistry is a complex science, to study it is necessary to pay attention to the topic being studied, and it depends mainly on the teacher, and if

he has enough knowledge, qualifications, skills, and methods to teach, it is possible to arouse the interest of a student who is not interested in science. We introduce students to specialize in the 1st year, general pedagogy in the 2nd year, in which they are taught teaching methods, we apply them in practice, what we learn in school. To make the lesson interesting, it is considered an effective way to organize games, for example, to divide the class into two equal groups, to conduct different questions and answers on the subject. The use of pictures, models, handouts and exhibitions makes the lesson much more interesting, motivates students to be active and increases their enthusiasm for the lesson, which we use all the time. In our practical lessons, we divide the topics and pass on the lessons to my classmates and create new methods of teaching ourselves, to give an example, the new method I used: in the lesson, using various exhibitions, handouts questions and pictures, I passed the lesson and at the end put small incentives of 4 different colors (Pink, Green, Yellow, Brown) on the table, and told everyone to choose the color of the stimulus and sit in their seats. At the beginning they didn't understand anything, then I ordered the students who received the pink stimulus to get up and explained the condition of the game to them, the condition was that the students who got up had to tell me what I said to each other on the topic I passed without repeating what they said, the student who could not say would be expelled from the game at the end of the day, the remaining 3 students will be evaluated with 5 marks if the information they said passed 15, The 3 students who come out of the first game are required to draw a 12-page notebook on the surface of the topic, the method I created is that if this game is repeated every lesson, the students will be attentive to the lesson and this is useful.

The methodological approaches used in teaching chemistry are mainly divided into two groups: traditional and modern. Traditional methods (lectures, demonstrations of experiments, laboratory classes) are widely used to increase students' knowledge. However, such methods can often lead to passive learning.

Modern approaches

1. Problem-based learning: Give students tasks that require problem-solving. This approach encourages students to think logically, analyze problems and come up with creative solutions.

2. Experiential learning: Students learn through hands-on experience. For example, in laboratory classes, students perform chemical reactions themselves and analyze the results.

3. Collaborative Learning: Encourage students to work in groups. This method helps develop social skills and students learn from one another.

Innovative technologies

In modern education, various innovative technologies are introduced. These include:

1. Virtual labs: Students can conduct chemistry experiments through online simulations. This is especially useful for risky experiments, which means that it is possible to safely skip labs that are risky to themselves, just through a single screen, to find out what the result will be.

2. Gamified learning: Students learn chemistry topics in the form of games. For example, interactive games can be designed to memorize chemical formulas. For example, organizing games linking to something else they are interested in so that it is easy to remember, at school children pay more attention not only to chemistry but to the science they are interested in, through games both chemistry and self-interest in science increases, for example, it is possible to ask a student studying biology (which elements are involved in the process of photosynthesis?) questions and assignments.

3. Mobile applications and electronic platforms: The quality of teaching can also be improved by developing mobile applications that allow students to learn chemistry issues and experiences online, and by giving them tasks such as conducting various experiments in these applications and recording their classification.

Important methods used to engage students in the lesson:

1. **Active participation:** Creating opportunities for students to ask questions, discuss and exchange ideas in order to actively participate in the lesson, and ask each student questions and tasks related to the topic.

2. **Personalized learning:** Give students individualized tasks based on their interests and abilities, which will boost their motivation.

3. **Self-assessment and reflexion:** Allowing students to assess their own knowledge and encouraging them to exchange ideas during the learning process, assignments like these are good ways to engage students.

Teachers' opinion: Different teachers share their experiences about methods of teaching chemistry. As many of them have pointed out, it's important to make the lesson interactive and to transform students from active listeners to active participants. Teachers should share their experiences to make the learning process more engaging and effective.

Effective methods for teaching chemistry are based on many methods. The most common and effective methods among them are:

1. Typescript (Experiential) Methods

Students will be able to consolidate theoretical knowledge in practice by experimenting in chemical laboratories. This method has an important role in enhancing the scientific interest of the students.

2. Problem solving method

Students are given complex problems or issues and develop analytical and critical thinking skills by solving them.

3. Visual methods (exhibition lessons)

Using visual tools such as pictures, graphs, videos, models, and diagrams to explain chemical processes makes the lesson fun and understandable.

4. Interactive methods

Involving students in discussions, working in groups and exchanging knowledge using the "converse" method enliven the learning process.

5. Gaming Technology

Didactic games, chemistry quizzes and interactive projects will encourage students to gain a deeper knowledge of science.

6. Problem of lim

During the lesson, the teacher poses various problems and together with the students looks for ways to solve them. This method develops creative thinking.

7. Self-manifestation on the topic (presentation methodology)

Students study a particular topic on their own and present it to other classmates. This develops among them in-depth mastery of the topic and communication skills. Each method has its own advantages and disadvantages, but combining them personally in the course process can lead to an effective result.

New methods and recommendations

1. Revolutionary teaching methods: Giving students real-life situations to solve chemistry problems. For example, organizing project work between groups to solve environmental problems.

2. **Cross-Course:** Combining chemistry with other disciplines (biology, physics, engineering) and showing students the subject they are studying.

3. **Mastering the learning process:** Give students weekly tests and fun exercises to review and review what they've learned during class.

4. **Collaboration on online platforms:** Encourage students to share experiences with each other through online platforms, such as working with and researching chemistry courses through forums and social media. I came up with the following method to create an innovative method to make my chemistry lesson more effective and interesting. The methodology, which promotes interactivity, practice, teamwork, and creative minding of the students, has been called "Explore, Analyze, Create and Share". This method deepens the learning of students by deepening each stage.

I have come up with an interesting and comprehensive method for passing a chemistry lesson, and I hope that this method will come in handy for teachers. The method, which aims to promote interactivity, practice, teamwork and creative thinking

of the students, has been called "Explore, Analyze, Inquire and Share". This method deepens the learning of students by deepening each stage.

Discover, Analyze, Create, and Share

1. Explore – (Initial Experience): At the beginning of the course, a small, fun, and easy-to-understand experiment is conducted to discover a new topic. This experience provides motivation to get to the topic and keeps students interested in the topic. For example, for a subject of chemical reactions one can show the reaction of colored substances (for example, the change of color of an indicator in the reaction of acid and alkali).

2. Analyze – (Mastering Theoretical Knowledge): After students see the experience, they move on to the theoretical part. In this, the teacher reveals the key concepts and is analyzed together with the students. By encouraging students to answer questions, they develop critical thinking skills. For example, you can ask questions such as: "Why did the indicator change color?" or "What products does this reaction produce?"

3. Create – (Hands-on and Team Project): Students are given the opportunity to work in small teams. They theoretically apply their acquired knowledge in practical practice. For example, in a team project, they will be tasked with making a special poster or video demonstrating chemical reactions, or testing small experiments in laboratory conditions. This process fosters teamwork and creativity.

4. Share – (Presentation of results and exchange of ideas): Each team presents the results of their project or experience to their classmates. During this phase, students can see each other's work, ask questions and share feedback. At the same time, at the end of the lesson, they will briefly describe how they felt and what they learned, which will develop the skill of self-reflection.

The advantages of the method are

1. Motivation – Motivation increases through hands-on experience on the topic as the lesson begins with fun.

2. Development of skills – Forms critical thinking, teamwork, creativity and communication skills.

3. Strengthening of learning – Theoretical knowledge is strengthened through experiments, which helps students to master the lesson more effectively.

4. Reflection – At the end of the lesson, students share their thoughts to reinforce their knowledge.

By introducing this method it is possible to increase the interest of students in the science of chemistry and improve their mastery of the subject.

Recommendations for teachers on conducting chemistry lessons

Make a plan: When planning the lesson, set specific goals. At the beginning, main points, and conclusion of each lesson you should show students what you plan to study. This will help the students understand what's important in the classroom. **Providing interactivity:** Disciplines like chemistry require practice. When explaining the theory, encourage students to participate with experiments and examples. It improves their understanding. **Integration with other disciplines:** Chemistry is related to many other disciplines, such as biology, physics, and mathematics. Learning these disciplines together gives students a better insight. **Simple examples:** Give simple, real-life examples before teaching a chemistry class. Bring examples from everyday life, such as showing how chemistry reactions are used in cooking or household chores. **Visual Materials:** Chemistry concepts can often be complex and abstract. The use of diagrams, images, videos and interactive materials provides more visual aid to readers. **Patience and repetition:** New teachers can sometimes lose patience in teaching, but chemistry lessons for students can sometimes take time. It is important to repeat the lesson in small steps and help the students to master. **Questions and answers:** Asking students questions and hearing their feedback throughout class increases student engagement. It is necessary to support their interests and clarify when they do not understand. **Development of critical thinking:** In the science of chemistry, analyzing problems and finding solutions to them motivates students to think scientifically. Teaching students to solve problems with an immersive approach develops critical thinking. Use of

experiments and laboratory work: In chemistry classes, laboratory work is especially important. This allows students to apply theoretical knowledge in practice and increases their interest in experimentation. Understanding students' interests: Every student learns differently, so identifying their interests and needs, organizing lessons accordingly, has a big impact on teacher success.

Conclusion and recommendations

The use of modern and innovative approaches to the teaching of chemical sciences allows to improve the quality of students' education and provide them with in-depth knowledge. It is recommended that teachers incorporate interactive and practical activities into the lesson, use new technologies and develop rapport with students.

Another important perspective is that teachers need to constantly update their knowledge and be ready to change pedagogical approaches. Chemistry, due to its dynamic nature, needs to be constantly updated, and teachers play an important role in this process.

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